

Modelling Clean Energy Transition Pathways in Developing Countries: The Case of Brazil

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Executive Summary

As a result of the Paris Agreement, Brazil formulated its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) regulations, updated in 2023. It stipulates that Brazil must reduce emissions by 48% in 2025 and 53% in 2030, compared to 2005 levels (MMA,2023). In other words, by 2050, everything the country emits must be offset by carbon sequestration sources, such as forest planting, biome restoration, or other technologies. This report examines the challenges of meeting objectives in the face of increasing electricity demand and climate change.

Therefore, three scenarios were evaluated using the open-source modelling system OSeMOSYS: Business-As-Usual (BAU), Implementation and Expansion of Offshore Wind Generation (EOL), and Commitment to Net Neutral Emissions by 2050 (NDC). In the BAU scenario, the consequences of maintaining the percentage composition of each energy generation technology in the energy matrix are presented. This is intended to serve as a reference for the formulation of public policies for the energy transition. The NDC scenario examines which technologies can replace polluting power generation, while the EOL scenario examines whether decarbonization can be achieved by 2050 through investment in offshore wind farms.

In the third scenario, we aim to investigate the effect of offshore wind generation on the grid. This is due to its identification as a medium-term expansion candidate in the analysis conducted under the 'Ten-Year Energy Expansion Plan' (PDE, 2029). Additionally, there are ongoing projects in Brazil's environmental licensing process.

1. Introduction

Modeling future scenarios is crucial for analyzing and optimizing Brazil's emissions targets and electricity generation costs. Brazil has set ambitious goals of limiting emissions to 48% by 2025, 53% by 2030, and achieving a neutral emissions

balance by 2050 (MMA, 2023). To achieve these goals, the mix of electricity generation technologies in the Brazilian matrix can be adjusted through modeling, such as OSeMOSYS applications. This approach shows promise for studying and improving the generation mix of the matrix.

Brazil's energy mix is primarily made up of renewable sources. Renewable sources accounted for 85.7% of the installed capacity for electricity generation between 2015 and 2024. This includes hydroelectric (49.5%), solar photovoltaic (16.10%), wind (12.50%), and biomass plus biogas (7.60%). The use of renewable energy sources has resulted in a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. Future scenarios present challenges, such as the stagnation in the growth of hydropower potential, which could affect emission rates and the cost per kWh.

To reduce greenhouse gas emissions in Brazil's energy matrix, the main focus should be on decreasing emissions from fossil fuel generation sources. Currently, 14.30% of Brazil's installed power generation comes from fuel oil, diesel, coal, and natural gas. Fossil fuels are the main source of emissions in Brazil's energy matrix, although other sources can also contribute to direct and indirect emissions. Balancing low emissions with low energy costs presents a challenge for future scenarios and projections.

The historical survey of the Brazilian energy scenario raises questions about future prospects. This text discusses the maintenance of the current Brazilian energy matrix (BAU); the potential contributions of an offshore generation to the Brazilian electricity matrix (EOL), and the future scenario for fossil fuels with reduced emissions (NDC).

2. Methodology

OSeMOSYS is an open-source linear modeling system that can predict the optimal evolution of a country's energy matrix. The OSeMOSYS modeling framework was chosen for the long-term analysis of the Brazilian energy system due to its ability to minimize costs, comply with emission limits, and meet demand constraints. The base model for this work assignment was the 'Starter Kit' provided by Carla Cannone (2021). To calibrate the model, we updated the installed capacities and energy generation history for the years 2015-2022 using data from the annual national energy balance reports.

Based on reports provided by the Ministry of Mining and Energy (PNE, 2050), three scenarios were evaluated: the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) scenario and the implementation and expansion scenario of offshore wind farms (EOL). Figure 1 summarizes the main characteristics of these scenarios.

- In the BAU scenario, the expansion of new renewable energy technologies is low, including photovoltaic energy, nuclear energy and biomass. No emission limits are imposed, and energy sources are updated based on historical trends, maintaining the same technological proportions and conditions as in previous years. This scenario explores the lowest-cost trajectory and provides a reference for further analysis.
- The NDC scenario aims to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, exploring cost-effective alternatives to renewable sources. However, we restrict the use of wind technology due to its negative impacts on biodiversity, deforestation, and habitat suppression, which make it difficult to obtain environmental licensing for implementation.
- The EOL scenario considers a progressive insertion of offshore wind technology. This scenario is being analyzed due to the intermittent nature of photovoltaic energy and recent investments in this technology by large Brazilian companies, such as Petrobras (UFRJ, 2023), to enable the energy transition of their operations.

Figure 1 - Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling.

3. Results and Discussion

As energy consumption increases in all scenarios, energy generation also rises accordingly. Figure 2 illustrates the gradual increase in power generation, reaching approximately 8000 PJ, 14000 PJ, and 7000 PJ in the BAU, NDC, and EOL scenarios, respectively. The key distinction between the NDC scenario and others lies in the necessity to electrify the transportation and heating sectors for decarbonization.

In the NDC scenario, fossil fuel production is replaced by onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar energy. The total electricity production from these renewable energy technologies is expected to reach approximately 12000 PJ by 2050, indicating significant potential for expansion compared to the 3000 PJ achieved by 2050 in the BAU scenario.

Figure 2 - Power generation 2020-2050 by technology.

Figure 3 - Installed capacity 2020-2050 by technology.

In figure 3, the difference between the installed capacities between 2040 and 2050 in the scenarios, highlighted in the NDC scenario, may be an effect of the difference in the capacity factor of the technologies selected by the model. A typical capacity factor for solar photovoltaic generation is around 29% while hydroelectric generation can have a capacity factor of around 62%.

Moreover, there are some onshore wind expansion projects that are currently experiencing social and environmental conflicts, which are causing delays in the licensing process that stakeholders weren't expecting. To tackle this dual conflict, the recommendations from the national plan of energy expansion were applied to the modelled case, specifically through the parameter of totalmaxcapacity.

This solution prevents the onshore wind turbines from being the optimal solution for this issue. The implementation of the constraint had a significant impact on the expansion of the system. As stated in the publicly available document, there's plan alternative defining a limit of 50 GW projected on installed capacity for the least-cost technology.

Figure 4 - Annual emissions 2015-2050.

In the EOL scenario, offshore wind energy is introduced from 2035 and investment is increased until 2050, resulting in reduced emissions from 2035 to 2045, as shown in Figure 4. However, zero emissions are not achieved until 2050. In the NDC scenario, Osemosys suggests investing in photovoltaic energy generation due to wind generation limitations imposed on the model.

Figure 5 - Total discounted system cost 2020-2050.

Total costs include capital, fixed, and variable costs associated with the development of the energy system. The total cost estimates for the BAU, NDC and EOL scenarios are US\$1351 billion, US\$4567 billion and US\$3413 billion, respectively. Decarbonizing the energy system requires higher investments beyond the financing needs in the BAU scenario, as shown in Figure 5.

Brazil's electricity matrix is composed of 88% renewable energy, while the energy matrix is only 47%. To achieve decarbonization, it is necessary to electrify other sectors, such as transport and heating, and therefore the NDC scenario in particular requires greater investment.

Therefore, as future work, we propose simulating a scenario that invests in solar and wind energy as possible alternatives to pollution sources. Additionally, we suggest using biomass as a dispatchable source to ensure the ideal functioning of the electrical system.

7. Conclusion

Based on this study, we recommend that Brazil invest in diversifying its renewable energy sources. While photovoltaic energy is cheaper to implement, it is highly dependent on solar irradiation and has a relatively short lifespan for solar panels. Conversely, offshore wind energy, though more expensive, can ensure continuous production even during nighttime. However, it's important to acknowledge that while renewable energy sources are vital for increasing electricity production and transitioning to cleaner energy, they are intermittent and may not be available during peak hours when dispatchable sources such as hydro and thermal energy are necessary.

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By 2050, it is recommended that all energy service/use disclosures in the country take steps to mitigate their actual contributions to climate change. This report carefully analyses the challenges of meeting this objective in the face of increasing electricity demand and the need for a sector-wide conversion to clean, emission-free sources. It proposes a path forward and provides guidance on how to make correct assumptions to tackle climate change.

Efforts should be made to integrate Brazil into regional instances in a way that can address various queries.

This fragment discusses the use of biofuels as a primary policy for transitioning to a more sustainable transportation matrix.

As well energy efficiency actions which have been emphasised as a paradigm for energy systems in Brazil since 2001. This continues to be an important task, especially as we are working towards achieving carbon neutrality. Careful consideration should be given to the best approach for balancing the grid and managing demands in sectors that are highly dependent on the system's steam.

This is crucial to ensuring a sustainable and reliable energy supply, with particular attention to accessibility for all. It is worth noting, however, that this latter assumption mainly applies to the north region, which represents 1.7% of Brazil not connected to SIN's transmission and distribution system.

And as modelled by the group, that should remain isolated.

The next step after making this decision is to improve data transparency. It is important to emphasize the significance of analyses in various contexts and how to obtain additional benefits based on robust and credible contexts, taking into account the role of each sector, and, intermittency and energy storage of installed systems.

This will help to improve the H2 project and consolidate cost-reducing policies that have been successfully implemented elsewhere and adopted to minimize project expenditure. This region of Latin America is situated in close proximity to the intertropical convergence zone and possesses considerable potential for offshore exploration, whilst water is abundantly available.

This research aims to examine the feasibility of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. The study measures the necessary investments for diversifying installed capacity, particularly through offshore wind farms and solar PV expansion; emphasizes the importance of establishing a proper energy base that can guarantee a stable electricity supply, especially during peak periods, without being affected by the rapidness of intermittent and clean energy sources expansion.

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